

AVAI: a Tool for Expressive Music Visualization based on Autoencoders and Constant Q Transformation

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes an approach using machine learning to extract sound expressiveness and translate it into light. An autoencoder was trained on several musical examples, thereby learning how to compress a constant Q transformed audio input, and then the latent space representation was used to generate visuals, in real time. A single interactive control parameter, the interpolation speed between new and current values, was made for customisation. The expressiveness of the visuals was tested through a variety of musical textures and genres rated by participants. Results indicate that participants found the system's translations to be visually expressive, and reacted very positively to the experience. The control parameter was tested for customization potential and found to be a good tool for allowing the participant to adjust the visual expression. The method for expressive visualization used in the system shows promise for further development.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of devices for visual representation of music has a history of several centuries, one of the first being the *Ocular Harpsichord* dating back to the 1700s. The device was first proposed by French mathematician Louis Bertrand Castel in 1725, and later designed by Johann Gottlieb Krüger in the essay *On a new kind of music, enjoyed by the eyes* in 1743 [1]. The *Clavilux* made by Danish born Thomas Wilfred in the 1920s had internal discs of stained glass that rotate along with a light bulb. The *Clavilux* projects a colorful composition onto a surface and can be manipulated by controlling the speed of the various discs.

In more modern history, the *Demoscene*, hailing from the 1980s with the home computer revolution, was a movement creating audiovisual programs that would show off the skills of the creator [2]. Software was subject to programmers who would attempt to build the most impressive visualizations, which grew to a culture with people competing to create the most compelling algorithms with minimally-capable hardware.

Contemporary digital arts are entering the era of machine learning, which is being explored for its multi-modal capa-

bilities. *The Deep Music Visualizer* [3] is a project that utilises interpolation features between images, and uses musical features like volume, tempo and pitch to drive the interpolations of the image features.

The importance of the combination of visuals and sound is apparent as demonstrated by (W. E. Hanser and R. E. Mark, 2013). They found that music with an emotional rating can affect the perception of a visual. [4]

For real time application, the contextual translation from sound to light is often based on pre-programmed responses and manual inputs, which requires constant attention from a video jockey (VJ) or a lighting designer to directly manipulate the visual output. The aim of this study is to show an expressive connection between the real time input sound and an output visual, through the use of an *autoencoder*.

Figure 1. Illustration of Thomas Wilfred playing the *Clavilux*. [5]

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Audio Visualisation

In recent years, visualisation of audio has been used in a variety of ways for academic purposes. A visualisation of real time musical expression has been done by tracking tempo and loudness, showing the musical expression by different artists [6]. And in participatory arts, mood-based visualisation has been made by using the participant's physiological arousal along with the music to generate visuals [7].

2.2 Autoencoder

The autoencoder as seen in Fig 2 is a Neural Network architecture, where the input and output layers are of the same dimensions, with the middle layer being a bottleneck. The autoencoder functions by learning how to compress the given input to a smaller size in the bottleneck layer (encoding), and then reconstruct the data based on

the compressed representation (decoding). The bottleneck layer of the autoencoder is known as the latent space.

Figure 2. Model of the autoencoder architecture with the bottleneck layer being the compressed representation of the input.

This study focuses on the translation of sound into light using the latent space, as a feature extraction method. When data is compressed and then reconstructed, only the most important information would be used for reconstruction. The representation found in the latent space is a set of features that can be used as descriptors, and can act as a dimensionality reduction method, by reducing the complexity of the input signal. This can be seen in the project by Terence Broad and Mick Grierson "Blade Runner Autoencoded" where the entirety of the 1982 film Blade Runner has been reconstructed with the use of an autoencoder. [8]

Autoencoders were chosen over PCA [9] as a dimensionality reduction technique, because it can handle non-linear data and is able to perform faster after training. Anomaly detection is another use of autoencoders for which it outperforms linear PCA [9]. Autoencoders have been used for noise reduction and speech enhancement [10], the results of which show better performance with deeper networks. Autoencoders have been used for language generation where an autoencoder is able to encode text, and reconstruct it coherently [11].

In this project the music is mapped by using an autoencoder trained with music, and using the resulting latent space values directly as the brightness values driving a real-time visualization based on a pixel shader. Color saturation of the shader was set to 0 to ensure simplicity in comprehension of the dynamic structure of the latent space. Expectations were to find a temporal structure in the latent space representative of the music.

3. METHODS

3.1 Building a neural network

3.1.1 Preparing the training dataset

A dataset consisting of various music tracks was transformed with a constant Q transform (CQT) [12]. An early implementation of the system was utilising the raw signal as input for the network, but it was discarded in favor of a massive reduction in network size from 1024 to 64 input layer, which reduced training time. With a sample rate

of 44100 Hz, the 1024 samples is 23.2 ms. The hop size is equal to frame size with no overlap. Sampling frequencies up to 22000 Hz requires a sampling frequency at least double the frequency because of the Nyquist frequency to avoid aliasing [13].

A constant Q transform (CQT) is an alternative to the fast fourier transform (FFT). Where the FFT converts a signal from a time domain into the frequency domain, by analysing the frequencies present in the signal and dividing into a number of frequency bands, the CQT utilises the same principle but uses a different methodology of band division as it is divided by octaves instead of an even spacing. The human hearing covers approximately ten octaves from 20Hz to 20KHz with each octave being double the frequency of the previous.

Dividing the frequency bands in respect to the octaves instead of the absolute frequency, mimics the human hearing capacity, as we are more sensitive on perceiving small changes at lower frequencies, rather than at high frequencies. In other words, it allows an allocation of more frequency bands for the lower end of the frequency spectrum, which helps to emphasize the importance of perception of those frequencies to humans. Another reason for choosing an octave spacing is that octaves are universal between musical cultures. The chromatic scale most commonly used in western musical tradition divides an octave into 12 pitches, while for instance Gamelan music in Indonesia divide it into 7 [14]. Building the system on an octave spacing would allow the system to generalise over cultural differences in pitch divisions, by choosing the training dataset for the network.

The choice of music to build the dataset was done by choosing aurally different music, which was verified by visually evaluating the CQT spectrograms. The dataset used for training can be seen in Fig. 3 where three different tracks can be distinguished:

Figure 3. Spectrogram of the constant Q transformed dataset used for training.

- From the left, the first is a track called *Sorry I Am Late (Pig & Dan Remix)* by *Kollektiv Turmstrasse*, and is a *house* track signified in the CQT by a repetitive low frequency seen towards the bottom of the spectrogram. In the middle there is a *build up* which can be distinguished by the lack of low frequency content and an increasing amount of higher frequency content.
- Second is a track by *Infinite Body* called *Dive*, which

is known as *drone* music. It is signified by gradually evolving textural sound across the entire frequency spectrum.

- Last track is from the polish classical music, and film music composer *Wojciech Kilar* called *Love Remembered* composed for the film *Bram Stoker's Dracula* (1992). It is signified by a varied but rhythmic content of mid to high frequency bands.

The last part of the spectrogram is black because a section of noise gated silence was introduced to the dataset.

3.2 Neural Network Architecture

The Keras [15] library for Python was used for the implementation. Programming was done in the Python environment Jupyter [16].

3.2.1 Neural Network Setup

The activation function used for the architecture was *rectified linear unit* (ReLU). Activation functions define how any given neuron in the network will react to an input value. In the case of ReLU, any value below 0 will yield a 0. And any value above 0 will correspond to the value linearly. The advantages of using ReLU is that it is computationally simple, reducing training time. Moreover, ReLU suffer less from the vanishing gradient problem. The optimizer used was *adaptive moment estimation* (Adam) [17]. The loss function used was *mean squared error* (mse). MSE calculates the loss based on the difference between the output values and the input values. These values can be higher and lower, therefore can produce differences that are both positive and negative numbers. Squaring the numbers before calculating the mean will ensure that negative values will not falsely minimize the calculated loss.

Previously used for speech recognition [18] *Long Short Term Memory* (LSTM) [19] was thought to be useful for the same distinctions in music as it is able to in speech. The much longer training time of the LSTM autoencoder made it very difficult to iterate the architectures within the project time frame. This steered development away from the use of LSTM and the idea was discarded for a more simplistic approach to reach a minimalist architecture. The resulting neural network is a shallow 64-8-64 dense configuration which is seen in Fig. 4.

3.2.2 Training the network and training validation

The network was trained 100 epochs, and ended with a loss of 0.0056 which did not improve over the past 25 epochs of training. When the trained model is introduced to the training dataset, it is able to decode the values of the latent space seen in the spectrogram in Fig. 5 which indicates a successful training.

3.3 Implementation

The trained model can be utilised with real time audio input, from a microphone or by using any audio routing software. The system records an audio frame and makes a constant Q transform which is then used as input for the trained

Figure 4. A model of the network architecture used with 3 dense neural network layers in an autoencoder structure with input size 64, latent space size 8 and output size 64

Figure 5. Spectrogram of a constant Q transformed audio track, above is the original, and below is the decoded spectrogram reconstructed from the latent space.

model. The values from the latent space are then extracted and flattened into a one dimensional array, normalized and sent to Touch Designer with the OSC protocol. The OSC message is received by Touch Designer and then used to manipulate a shader coded with GLSL. Moreover, Touch Designer was used for real time parameterization and projection mapping.

The shaders simulate the effect of a fluorescent light tube mounted on a concrete wall. Eight identical light fixtures have been used, each one utilizing a single latent vector value, in order to control the brightness of this light. That way the fluorescent tubes represent a direct visualisation of the latent vectors. An example of how a single latent vector frame looks can be seen in Fig. 6.

Logarithmic interpolation was used, as a low pass filter, in order to reduce sudden changes in the latent space values. Changing the interpolation speed of the latent space values was used as a visualization parameter and was added for convenience and integrated as part of the experiment. Low interpolation values results in faster changes in the lighting, and a higher value results in slower changes. A

Figure 6. Example of the GLSL shaders that are mapped in the space. Here all 8 fluorescent tubes are on 1 screen whereas in the space they are projection mapped on 3 screens and arranged differently. Projection mapping allows precise control to ensure a completely flat projection on the screens, independent of the projector position.

Figure 7. Model of the system architecture.

tablet was used as an OSC controller for the interpolation speed. For clarity, this control parameter was called "update speed" to ensure that participants would understand it's function. The slider seen in Fig. 11 as "Slider 1" was used in the OSC app to control a parameter in Touch Designer. The value divided the difference between the current frame and the previous frame by a range of 1-400. At setting 1, every frame updated with the full difference between the values and at setting 400, it divided that value by 400 making the visuals appear more calm.

3.4 Experiment Setup

Twenty-one participants consisting of university students and professors, were enrolled in this study. The experiment was done in the Lighting Design Laboratory of AAU. The lab is rectangle shaped with white walls and the ability to block light with curtains. Three short throw DLP projectors were used for this setup, which was put under a table in the middle of the room. The participants had access to a tablet, to control the music being played and the interpolation speed. A video showing the visuals in the space can be seen here: <https://bit.ly/2VPF6YF>

The experiment was executed in 3 phases. Phase 1 and 2

Figure 8. Screenshot from the app used to control interpolation speed of the visualisation.

Figure 9. Top view layout of the experiment setup with 3 projectors, 3 walls used as projection screens, 1 tablet and 2 speakers.

evaluates with expressiveness of the visualisation of textural sounds with 2 different update speed settings (fast and slow). Phase 3 evaluates the expressiveness of visualisations of the participant's choice of music from the Spotify library, and the potential of the control parameter(update speed).

Participant were asked to read the project description and were allowed to ask questions, to ensure that they understand the scope and objectives of this study. The application installed on the tablet to control the update speed was explained. The participant was informed that they are allowed to explore the space. Phase 1 starts with 4 different sounds from the Spotify library: 1. Rivers and Streams - Babbling Brook, 2. Granular - White Noise - 200 Hz, 3. White Noise Collectors - Human Heartbeat, 4. Singing Bowls of Tibet - Tibetan Singing Bowl. The sounds were played with an update speed setting of 1 (very fast). Then, the participant answered a questionnaire, using the same tablet to evaluate the expressiveness of the visual on a likert scale from 1 (Not at all) to 10 (Very much). The question asked in the questionnaire is: "You have just listened to the sound of [track]. How expressive would you say the visual was of the sound?" The evaluation was executed after every sound for a total of 4 times in phase 1, and 4 times in phase 2.

Phase 2 repeats phase 1, now with the update speed set

Figure 10. Picture of the experiment showing the table, and the projections from 2 of the 3 projectors.

at 200(calm). Expressiveness was evaluated in the same manner.

Figure 11. The OSC control app could be used to change the update speed of the visuals between 1-400.

In phase 3, the participant was given the tablet to change the music and control the update speed seen in Fig. 11. The participant was allowed 10 minutes to play with the system. After 10 minutes the participant would continue the questionnaire, which evaluated two facets of the system: first the expressiveness of the input to output mapping of the AVAI system. Second the potential of the control parameter of the update speed to match the aesthetic tone of the music and the visual. The participant was allowed to decide the music as to ensure a wider variety of genre choice and to avoid bias.

The questions asked in phase 3 in point form:

- What are your initial thoughts of the system? (Paragraph answer)
- How correlated did you feel the visuals were with the music that you listened to? (Likert scale from 1 (Not at all) to 10 (Very much))
- Did you find yourself changing the update speed a lot during the listening session to match the visuals and the music? (Likert scale from 1 (Not at all) to 10 (Very much))
- Did you feel that the control parameter to change the update speed of the visuals is sufficient to match the aesthetic tone of the music and the visual? (Yes/No)

- If no, can you explain/elaborate? (Paragraph answer)
- Any comments? (Paragraph answer)

4. RESULTS

4.1 Phase 1 and 2

The 4 questions evaluating expressiveness of the sounds with the likert-scale will be referred to as Q1-Q4. Phase 1 and phase 2 will be referred to as P1 and P2. Q1 = Rivers and Streams - Babbling Brook. Q2 = Granular - White Noise - 200 Hz. Q3 = White Noise Collectors - Human Heartbeat. Q4 = Singing Bowls of Tibet - Tibetan Singing Bowl.

Figure 12. Diverging stacked bar chart of the likert grades showing the distribution of expressiveness grades from 1-10 of all 4 songs (Q1-Q4) in both phases (P1 and P2). Fully saturated red being the grade 1, and fully saturated blue meaning the grade 10.

The mean grades with standard deviation seen in Fig. 13 shows the comparison between the ratings for P1 and P2. Note the significant drop of Q3 from P1 to P2, and the increase of Q4 with a lower standard deviation from P1 to P2.

4.1.1 Wilcoxon

The Wilcoxon test was used to determine the statistical difference between P1 and P2 for each likert evaluation of the different sounds. Null hypothesis for the test: there is no difference in expressiveness between P1 and P2.

The differences in mean grades seen in Fig. 13, is confirmed by the Wilcoxon test as it can be seen that the null hypothesis can be rejected confidently for Q3 and Q4 to an alpha of 0.005.

Figure 13. Graph of the mean grades and standard deviation of Q1-Q4 in P1 and P2. Blue is P1 and Red is P2.

Alpha	0,001	0,005	0,01	0,025	0,05	0,10	0,20
Q1	H0	H0	H0	H0	H0	H0	H0
Q2	H0	H0	H0	H0	H0	H0	H1
Q3	H0	H1	H1	H1	H1	H1	H1
Q4	H0	H1	H1	H1	H1	H1	H1

Figure 14. Table of the results from the Wilcoxon test. H0 signifies an acceptance of the null hypothesis. H1 denotes a rejection of the null hypothesis.

4.2 Phase 3

4.2.1 Expressiveness of the system

The first question in P3 was: "How correlated did you feel the visuals were with the music that you listened to?"

The participants expressed a positive reaction to the system, which is presented in Fig. 15 and can also be seen in the mean grade = 7.1 with a standard deviation = 2.0.

4.2.2 Potential of control parameter

The first question about the control parameter: "Did you find yourself changing the update speed a lot during the listening session to match the visuals and the music?" This checks if the participants felt that they could find a setting for the update speed that would fit perfectly for an entire song, or even several songs. The mean grade was 7.3, and the standard deviation was 2.5.

This shows a high user engagement, meaning that the users were interacting a lot with the control parameter as they didn't feel that one specific setting would be perfect for a genre or even a specific part of a track. This can also be found in the paragraphed comments: "With slower music I liked to slide it more towards the right. Music with more beats needed more movement so I slid it more to the left".

Next question: "Did you feel that the control parameter to change the update speed of the visuals is sufficient to match the aesthetic tone of the music and the visual?"

How correlated did you feel the visuals were with the music that you listened to?

Figure 15. Diverging stacked bar chart of the likert grades showing the distribution of expressiveness grades from 1 (red) to 10 (blue). 4 of the grades were 5 or lower, 17 were 6 or higher.

Did you find yourself changing the update speed a lot during the listening session to match the visuals and the music?

Figure 16. Diverging stacked bar chart of the likert grades showing the distribution of user engagement. 5 of the grades were 5 or lower, 16 were graded 6 or higher.

As seen in Tab. 1, a majority of the participants felt that the control parameter was sufficient for them to match the aesthetic tone of the music and the visual. The majority of the participants that answered "no" would prefer to see the system also allowing for control of colors to match the music: "I feel some more interpretive layers are needed; color, shapes, movement, etc."

4.2.3 Paragraph answers

Common themes were found in the paragraphed comments:

- Mentioned a wish for color: 33.3%
- Mentioned accuracy of control parameter: 28.6%

The attitude towards the system was very positive:

- Commented positively about the system: 95.2%
- Commented neutrally about the system: 4.8%
- Commented negatively about the system: 0%

5. ANALYSIS

The participants responded positively to the system with no participant commenting negatively about the experience with 95.2% commenting positively and 4.8% neutrally. In terms of user based responses for system improvements,

Yes	No
12	9

Table 1. More than half of the participants felt that the control parameter was sufficient

33.3% mentioned a wish for color in the visuals which is also a subject for development and implementation. 28.6% mentioned the accuracy of the control parameter on the tablet application being too responsive in the lower end of the scale, but inconsequential in the higher end - this can be tested with an exponentially scaling slider instead of a linear one. The control parameter seems as a powerful tool for visualisation manipulation, but should be expanded upon as the control may seem too one dimensional for a fully expressive translation.

The mean grade for the evaluation of expressiveness of the system was 7.1, which along with the positive reaction from participants does express a successful translation from music to visual. As seen in Fig. 15, the reaction to the system and the experience was very positive with only 4 participants grading it below 5, and 7 grading it at a 9. One of the participants noted: "It makes the experience of the music more intense."

5.1 Wilcoxon

Referring to Fig. 14, a significant difference can be seen in Q3 and Q4 compared to Q1 and Q2. This coincides with the general mean score being higher in Q3 for P1 and Q4 for P2, illustrating the polar differences between P1 and P2 for Q3 and Q4. This means that the change in update speed polarised the perceived expressiveness of the visuals significantly for Q3 and Q4. This might be because of the sound of a water stream, and the sound of white noise is rhythmically incoherent, making it difficult for the participant to evaluate the expressiveness - or that the participant felt that the speed at which the visuals updated were irrelevant for the perceived expressiveness. This may indicate that the system is more expressive with more dynamic rhythmical content rather than a more rhythmically "static" sound like noise or running water.

5.2 Control

The aim for evaluating control parameters for the system is a matter of balance between the participant feeling in control, and being overwhelmed by options. With 57% of participants stating that the control parameter is enough, the control parameter for the update speed of a dynamic visual system indicates that it grants the user meaningful control through one parameter. More parameters should be added to address the wish for color integration in the system.

6. DISCUSSION

6.1 Experiment

The aesthetics of the installation setup may have had an effect on the scores. All the participants were introduced

to the project by reading the project poster which sought to ensure that they were not going to evaluate the aesthetics of the visuals, but the dynamic connection between the visual and the music. If this was completely clear to the participant cannot be known, only attempted to be communicated clearly by using a clear language. It may have been hard for the participants to distinguish if they were evaluating the entire experience of being in the space.

6.2 Technical improvements

Currently, there is an amount of frame loss in the system, possibly generating more volatile values from frame to frame. In spite of this, the system is able to produce expressive translations of music. A migration of the DSP operations would likely alleviate this concern.

6.3 Dataset

The dataset used is very small. However, the system has been able to represent temporal feature extraction which was perceived to be expressive of the music, in spite of the dataset's small size. It is expected that in terms of abstraction, the features are very low level, and therefore not truly dependent on procedural information but rather temporal shifts in frequency. This may explain why the system is able to expressively translate a much broader array of sounds based on only 22 minutes of samples.

6.4 Future Work

As suggested by Roche et.al (2019), deep or recurrent autoencoders perform better at signal reconstruction which means that the latent vectors may be more expressive of the input sound [20]. The working prototype of the system is not analysing time series, but only one frame of sound at any given moment. Further system development should re-investigate the options for either a deeper neural network configuration, and/or time series analysis with utilisation of LSTM nodes and the recurrent neural network methodology.

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